

PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL EXPECTATIONS AND SOCIAL IDEALIZATION PHENOMENA IN DETERMINING THE PROFESSIONAL STATUS OF A SCHOOL PSYCHOLOGIST IN THE GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article focuses on the scope of psychological service activities in the general secondary education system and identifies the similarities and differences between the social expectations and social idealization of the school psychologist and school students, who are the subjects of this system. The identified scientific facts were interpreted quantitatively and qualitatively.

Key words: psychological service, system, social expectation, social idealization, professional reflection, respondent, phenomenon.

The 21st century, many studies are being published about the increasing demand of society for psychological services [1;2;3] . Reputable organizations are reporting that this demand is increasing even more due to the global pandemic experienced by mankind [4]. According to the reports of the American Psychological Association, the number of complaints related to anxiety and depression has increased after the pandemic, and the demand for their treatment is increasing.

In addition, reasons such as the intensive social changes taking place in the world, population growth, urbanization, socio-psychological relations becoming complex, value devaluation, and the intensity of the information flow can be cited.

We will try to analyze some aspects of the increasing tendency of this demand on the example of the psychological service activity formed in the general secondary education system of Uzbekistan. Why the psychological service in the general secondary education system? We will give some reasons for this.

lack of formation of a psychological service system that serves all categories of the population; that the processes of specialization in the system of training psychologists are just beginning;

lack of development of specific qualification requirements of specialists serving different population groups;
weakness of perceptions of the importance of psychological services and the need for psychological help in the mentality of the population;
lack of psychological service organizations (associations, non-governmental organizations, etc.) and centers specializing in certain areas of social activity;
lack of establishment of a licensing system for psychological service specialists in various spheres of social activity.

If we take the activity of the psychological service in the context of Uzbekistan, we know that only in the general secondary education system, which has a centralized management structure, the activity of the system is regulated at the level of the current legislation. We can say that this system covers a large part of the population of Uzbekistan. According to the information of the Ministry of preschool and school education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the 2022-2023 academic year, 6,407,828 students are studying in general secondary schools of the republic[6], while 509,443 teachers are teaching them[7]. According to statistical data, 1/5 of the population of Uzbekistan works directly in this system. We do not have accurate information about the number of students studying in general secondary schools of Uzbekistan. However, there is no doubt that their number is more than 7 million. If we make a conclusion based on this information, the general secondary education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan covers more than 14 million people. This means about 40% of the population of Uzbekistan. This system is a giant in terms of coverage of the country's population. There is no other such large system in the republic.

Psychological services also have their place in the general secondary education system. According to the information of the center of vocational guidance and psychological-pedagogical diagnosis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 13,864 practicing school psychologists are working in this system [5]. So, there is 1 practicing school psychologist for every 462 students in the schools of Uzbekistan.

In this article, while studying the specific characteristics of the professional status of practicing school psychologists operating in such a huge system, we tried to study the differences and similarities between the social idealization of school students in relation to the practicing school psychologist and the professional reflection of the school psychologist.

In order to study the social idealization of schoolchildren in relation to school psychologists and the professional reflection of school psychologists, a group of respondents was

formed in 3 districts of Fergana region (Uchkopriq, Bagdad and Altariq), consisting of school psychologists and high school students. They were asked a single question: "In your opinion, what kind of person should a practicing school psychologist be?". We analyzed the answers to this question using the method of content analysis and got the following results.

Mentioned by respondents	
personal and professional characteristics	
School psychologists	School students
Good listener	Beautiful
Knowledgeable	Responsible
Merciful	Merciful
Accessible	Understandable
Analytical	Considerable
Courtesy	Introductory
Cultured	Smart
Considerable	Courtesy
Sozamol	Sincere
The outlook is broad	Be open-minded
Demanding	Good listener
Can keep a secret	Can keep a secret
Patient	
Listener	

The table above shows all the personal and professional characteristics mentioned by the respondents.

During the research, the 5 most emphasized characteristics mentioned by the respondents were extracted and the following results were obtained.

In your opinion, what kind of person should a practicing school psychologist be?

School psychologists		School students	
Features	%	Features	%
Knowledgeable	22.70	Understandable	21.60
A good listener	15.90	Sincere	15.20
Courtesy	9.10	Merciful	13.60

Merciful	6.90	Beautiful	12.00
Cultured	6.80	Smart	8.80

As we mentioned above, we selected the most mentioned qualities from the respondents. In order to ensure the naturalness of the research, we left the adjectives chosen by the respondents as they were. These adjectives express a sufficient meaning in the context of the Uzbek language, and in the course of the article we will explain these personal adjectives with a sufficient level of commentary.

If we analyze the answers of practicing school psychologists and high school students, we will definitely come across some similar answers. For example, both groups of respondents chose the quality of kindness (School psychologists 6.90%; School students 13.60%). Therefore, it is important for both parties that the school psychologist should be kind. The fact that the quality "kindness" was selected by a particularly high percentage of students means that their need to expect kindness from adults is strongly expressed. School psychologists have also emphasized that this quality is necessary for a specialist providing psychological services. Let's check what this adjective means in Uzbek. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, this quality is defined as follows: "Kind 1 showing compassion, loving sincerely. 2 caregivers"[8] . So both parties showed their appreciation of the quality of kindness in social relations and professional activities.

Another phenomenon was highlighted in the responses of school psychologists and students. Despite the fact that the personal quality of their answers is expressed in different

words, they can be considered as complementary in content and expressing the common needs of both parties. In the case of school psychologists, the quality of "Good listener" was 15.90%, while the quality described as "Understanding" in the responses of schoolchildren showed the highest 21.60%. This result indicates that the school psychologist feels that when working with students, he should listen to them, communicate with them more, work directly with their problems, and use listening tactics more to feel the mental state of students. On the other hand, it is shown that the schoolboy needs a specialist who listens to him, who can stand in the position of understanding and not evaluating the emotions he is experiencing.

Now let's focus on the different aspects of the respondents' answers. In the responses of school psychologists, the quality "Educated" had the highest result (22.70%). In the answers of schoolchildren, the "Understanding" quality was 21.60%, that is, the highest result. It can be seen that there is a difference between the social expectations of school psychologists and school students and the phenomenon of idealization. While school psychologists believe that it is most important for a practicing psychologist to have professional knowledge, they express in their answers that schoolchildren need an expert who understands them. In fact, we can conclude that such a response from both parties is completely natural. But it turns out that school psychologists should understand that their professional knowledge loses its value if it is not sublimated into practice, if it does not work in natural conditions and complex social context. The responses of schoolchildren confirm that they expect a person who understands them from a knowledgeable and highly qualified specialist. Therefore, the system of training school psychologists and their professional development system, the general philosophy of psychological services in the general secondary education system should be aimed at finding a balance in this middle.

It is also worth analyzing the quality "Beautiful", which was not found in the answers of practicing school psychologists and occupied 12.00% in the answers of schoolchildren. The meeting of this quality in the students' answers shows that the specialist working with the youth category, especially the person conducting psychological activities, should pay attention to his appearance. It is found that a pleasant appearance is important in the social perception of schoolchildren. Of course, the school psychologist's appearance, which is pleasant to others, is an issue that deserves a separate study. This research should be carried out at the border of cultural studies, sociology and psychology.

Also, the adjectives "polite" (9.10%), "cultured" (6.80%) took the leading place in the responses of school psychologists, while the adjectives "sincere" (15.20%) and "smart" (8.80%) were mentioned the most in the answers of schoolchildren.

Within the framework of this study, an attempt was made to determine the specificity of the phenomena of social expectation and social idealization among practicing school psychologists and schoolchildren. There is no doubt that there is a need for systematic research in this direction. Emotional demands manifested in the phenomena of social expectation and social idealization must be taken into account in the training of psychologists working in the educational system, their qualification improvement and assessment systems. This approach serves to reduce the differences between the real possibilities and professional potential of the practicing school psychologist.

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